

Original article

The effect of hookworm infestation on haemoglobin concentration in pregnancy in Kano, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Hookworm infestation contributes significantly to anaemia in pregnancy in many tropical settings, thereby increasing fetomaternal morbidity and mortality. Up-to-date data from Kano, North-west Nigeria, were lacking. The study aimed to determine the prevalence of hookworm infestation among pregnant women in Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital and its association with haemoglobin concentration. **Materials and methods:** This cross-sectional prospective study enrolled 180 consenting pregnant women attending the antenatal clinic. Stool samples were examined by formol-ether sedimentation and Stoll's egg-counting technique. Haemoglobin concentration was measured at recruitment. Data were analysed using Epi Info version 3.5. The Mann-Whitney U test compared haemoglobin concentrations between infested and non-infested women due to the small and unequal group sizes. A P-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant. **Result:** The mean age of the participants was 27.5 ± 2.4 years. Five women (2.9%; 95% CI 0.45%–5.35%) harboured *Ancylostoma duodenale*; all infections were of light intensity (700 eggs per gram). The mean (SD) haemoglobin concentration of the infested group was 9.2 (1.1) g/dL compared with 11.1 (1.3) g/dL in the non-infested group (Mann-Whitney U test, P = 0.02; mean difference 1.9 g/dL, 95% CI -3.4 to -0.4 g/dL). The association between hookworm infection and lower haemoglobin remained statistically significant, but the small number of infected women and the lack of adjustment for confounders prevent causal inference. **Conclusion:** Hookworm infestation was present in 2.9% of the antenatal population and was associated with a lower haemoglobin concentration. Given the very small number of infected cases and the uncontrolled confounders, the clinical significance of this finding is uncertain. The study does not allow firm conclusions about the need for population-wide deworming.

Keywords: Anaemia, Haemoglobin, Hookworms, Kano, Pregnancy.

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Introduction

Hookworms (*Ancylostoma duodenale* and *Necator americanus*) are soil-transmitted helminths (STH) that infect humans through skin contact with infective third-stage larvae in warm, tropical, and subtropical soils.¹ The larvae penetrate the skin, migrate through the venous and lymphatic systems to the lungs, ascend the trachea, are swallowed, and mature into egg-laying adults in the small intestine.^{1,2} Trans-oral and lactogenic transmission have also been postulated.^{1,3} Anaemia is a well-recognised complication of hookworm infestation and represents a major cause of maternal morbidity and mortality.⁴⁻⁸ The World Health Organisation (WHO) defines anaemia in

pregnancy as a haemoglobin concentration below 11.0 g/dL,⁷ while many developing countries use a cut-off of <10.0 g/dL.⁸ Pregnant women are especially vulnerable because of increased iron demands and blood loss at delivery.¹⁰

In Kano, previous reports indicate that up to 17% of pregnant women have anaemia (using packed cell volume <30%), with a substantial proportion attributable to iron deficiency.^{5,6} In other endemic areas, moderate-to-severe anaemia in pregnancy has been attributed to STH, especially hookworm, in 30–54% of cases.^{14–17} Interventional studies have shown that deworming during pregnancy can improve haemoglobin concentration and reduce adverse birth outcomes.^{11,18–23}

Because recent, local data on the prevalence of hookworm and its impact on haemoglobin in pregnancy were unavailable, this study was undertaken to provide current evidence from Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital and to explore the potential need for routine anti-helminthic therapy.

Materials and methods

Study Area

The study took place at Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital, a tertiary referral centre in Kano metropolis, North-west Nigeria, from 6 January to 17 February 2015.

Study Design and Population

This was a descriptive cross-sectional study that systematically recruited 180 consenting pregnant women attending the antenatal clinic.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

All consenting pregnant women were eligible. Women who did not consent, those with clinically evident severe anaemia requiring urgent intervention, known sickle cell disease, HIV infection with Zidovudine-induced anaemia, or syndromic evidence of malaria, urinary tract infection, or respiratory tract infection were excluded.

Sample Size Determination

The minimum sample size for prevalence estimation was calculated using the formula $n = z^2p(q)/d^2$, yielding 160; this was increased to 180 to account for a 10% attrition rate. The study was not powered to detect a difference in mean haemoglobin between infected and uninfected women.

Sampling Procedure

An average of 200 women attended the clinic daily, yielding a sampling frame of approximately 800 over one week. The sampling interval ($K = 800/180 \approx 4$) was applied. Starting from a randomly chosen

point (2), every 4th eligible patient was recruited. Recruitment was completed over four clinic days.

Data and Sample Collection

Participants were asked to provide a fresh stool specimen at their next scheduled antenatal visit. Stool samples were collected over a period of six weeks, as the interval between visits varied. All specimens were transported in clean, dry, leak-proof, and labelled containers.

Laboratory Methods

Faecal samples were concentrated using the modified Ridley-Allen formol-ether sedimentation technique.²⁹ Two drops of sediment were mixed with iodine and examined under $\times 10$ and $\times 40$ objectives. Hookworm eggs and larvae were identified morphologically. The intensity of infection was determined by the Stoll egg-counting technique, classified as light (1–1,999 eggs per gram [epg]), moderate (2,000–3,999 epg), or heavy ($\geq 4,000$ epg).^{29,38}

Capillary blood for haemoglobin estimation was collected by the principal investigator at the time of recruitment (i.e., before stool collection). Haemoglobin concentration was determined using a portable haemoglobinometer.

Statistical Analysis

Data were entered and analysed with Epi Info version 3.5 (CDC, Atlanta, USA). Quantitative variables were summarised as mean \pm standard deviation or median and interquartile range, as appropriate. Qualitative variables were described as frequencies and percentages. Because only five women had hookworm infection, the Mann-Whitney U test was used to compare haemoglobin concentrations between infected and uninfected groups. A two-tailed P-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital Research Ethics Committee. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Results

Ten of the 180 enrolled women did not return stool samples, resulting in an attrition rate of 5.6% and leaving 170 complete records for analysis.

Socio-demographic Characteristics

Table 1 summarises the participants' characteristics. The mean age was 27.5 ± 2.4 years, with the majority (58.2%) aged 20–29 years. Most women had secondary (40.0%) or tertiary (53.5%) education.

Table 1: Socio-demographic Distribution of Study Participants (N=170)

Characteristic	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
<20	13	7.7
20–29	99	58.2
30–39	51	30.0
≥40	7	4.1
Educational Status		
None	1	0.6
Primary	8	4.7
Secondary	68	40.0
Tertiary	91	53.5
Islamic	2	1.2
Parity		
0	53	31.2
1–4	91	53.5
≥5	26	15.3
Trimester		
First (<14 weeks)	7	4.1
Second (14–27 weeks)	68	40.0
Third (≥28 weeks)	95	55.9

The median parity was 2 (range 0–11), and 53.5% were of parity 1–4. Over 95% of the women were in the second or third trimester, with a mean gestational age of 28 ± 2.1 weeks.

Prevalence of Hookworm Infestation

Five of the 170 stool samples contained hookworm ova, all identified as *Ancylostoma duodenale*, giving a prevalence of 2.9% (95% CI 0.45%–5.35%). All infections were of light intensity: the egg count was uniformly 700 epg (range across the five cases: 500–900 epg). Figure 1 illustrates the distribution of infestation.

Figure 1: Pie chart showing pattern of hookworm infestation among study participants - infested 2.9%, non-infested 97.1%

Haemoglobin Concentration and Hookworm Infection

The overall mean haemoglobin concentration was 10.2 g/dL (range 8.7–13.3 g/dL). Among the five infected women, the mean (SD) haemoglobin was 9.2 (1.1) g/dL, compared with 11.1 (1.3) g/dL in the 165 non-infected women (Mann-Whitney U test, $P = 0.02$). The mean difference was -1.9 g/dL (95% CI -3.4 to -0.4 g/dL). Table 2 displays this comparison. The mean gestational age of the infected women (29.1 ± 3.2 weeks) did not differ significantly from that of the uninfected group (28.0 ± 2.1 weeks), but the very small number of infected women precludes reliable comparison.

Table 2: Comparison of Haemoglobin Concentration by Hookworm Infection Status

Infection status	n	Mean Hb (g/dL)	SD	Median (IQR)	Test statistic	P-value
Hookworm infected	5	9.2	1.1	9.0 (8.5-9.9)	Mann-Whitney U = 201.5	0.02
Non-infected	165	11.1	1.3	11.2 (10.1-12.0)		

Discussion

The 2.9% prevalence of hookworm infection in this antenatal population is consistent with recent reports from other Nigerian and East African settings (ranging from 1% to 6.1%).^{4,30-35} Earlier data from Kano showed a similar prevalence (3.7%) among non-pregnant women of reproductive age,⁹ suggesting that the parasitic burden in this predominantly urban, educated population is low. The uniformly light intensity of infection (700 epg) further supports this view.

The observed difference of 1.9 g/dL in mean haemoglobin between infected and non-infected women was statistically significant. This magnitude is clinically meaningful on the surface, but the finding must be interpreted cautiously. First, the comparison is based on only five infected individuals, making the estimate highly unstable. The wide 95% confidence interval (-3.4 to -0.4 g/dL) overlaps with a minimal clinically important difference, and the p-value, while below 0.05, is a fragile indicator given the extreme group imbalance.

Second, and more importantly, several key causes of anaemia in pregnancy were not systematically excluded. Malaria, for instance, is endemic in Kano and can cause significant haematological changes even when asymptomatic. Nutritional iron deficiency, the most common cause of anaemia worldwide, was not assessed through dietary histories or iron studies. HIV, other chronic infections, and haemoglobinopathies were only partially addressed. Because these confounders could depress haemoglobin in the hookworm-positive group regardless of parasitic infection, the observed association cannot be interpreted as a causal lowering effect. Our study is therefore unable to disentangle the independent contribution of hookworm to anaemia.

The timing of haemoglobin measurement also warrants comment. Blood samples were drawn at recruitment, while stool was collected at the next antenatal visit, up to several weeks later. The physiological haemodilution of pregnancy could have contributed to a lower haemoglobin at the later visit, but because the infected group's haemoglobin was measured at recruitment, the effect would, if anything, bias the result toward the null. However, we cannot rule out the possibility that changes in the interval between infections or in nutritional status influenced the readings.

Earlier studies have recommended routine deworming during pregnancy based on evidence that anti-helminthic therapy improves haemoglobin levels and birth outcomes.^{11,18-23} Our findings do not contradict those guidelines, but the low prevalence and light intensity observed in this facility-based sample suggest that the absolute benefit of mass deworming in similar urban referral populations may be limited. The WHO's preventive chemotherapy thresholds are based on community-level surveys; therefore, this hospital-based study cannot directly inform population-level policy.²⁴ Despite these limitations, even light hookworm infections have been linked to subtle iron loss, and no infection should be dismissed.^{38,43} The global burden of hookworm disease remains substantial,^{44,45} and ongoing vaccine development underscores the need for continued attention.^{46,47}

Conclusion

Hookworm infestation occurred in 2.9% of pregnant women attending Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital and was associated with a statistically significant lower haemoglobin concentration. However, the very small number of infected cases, the imprecision of the estimate, and the lack of control for important confounders preclude attributing causality or drawing firm clinical

conclusions. This study does not provide a basis for modifying the current WHO deworming recommendations in this setting.

Recommendations

A large, multicentre study with rigorous control for confounders (malaria parasitaemia, iron status, gestational age, and nutritional intake) is needed to clarify the true impact of hookworm on haemoglobin in pregnancy. In the interim, the WHO guideline of preventive chemotherapy for at-risk populations should be maintained, while clinicians should also address other common causes of anaemia.

Limitations of the Study

The major limitations include: (i) The sample size was calculated for prevalence estimation, not for comparing haemoglobin means; the primary comparison is severely underpowered. (ii) Only five women were infected, leading to highly unreliable estimates and an inflated risk of both type I and type II error. (iii) Important confounders—malaria, nutritional deficiencies, asymptomatic bacteriuria, and HIV—were not excluded by laboratory testing. (iv) Haemoglobin and stool samples were collected at different time points. (v) The hospital-based sample, composed mainly of educated, urban-dwelling women, limits generalisability to rural populations where hookworm prevalence is likely higher.

Conflict of Interest

None declared.

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